

Alcoholic extract: Column chromatography of ethanolic extract over silica gel did not yield any crystalline compound.

Acknowledgement

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Mercurimetric Determination of Organotrithiocarbonates and A Method for the Analysis of Mercaptans

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ORGANOTRITHIOCARBONATES are the salts of the corresponding trithiocarbonic acids (I) and

are prepared through the reaction of mercaptans with carbon disulphide in the presence of an alkali:

They find applications¹ as flotation agents, vulcanisation accelerators, pesticides, plant defoliants, rust inhibitors, lubricating oil additives and modifiers in bulk styrene polymerisation. Some trithiocarbonates have recently been reported to possess activity as anti radiation drugs. In spite of their numerous applications in industry, agriculture and medicine, their determination has not received much attention. Verma and Kumar²⁻³ recently described some oxidimetric methods for the determination of these compounds in aqueous and non-aqueous media.

The fact that organotrithiocarbonates react with mercury and other heavy metals to form salts, is already known^{1,3,9}. The present communication reports a method for the determination of organotrithiocarbonates based on their tendency to react with metals to form salts. The use of mercury(II) is described for the first time for the determination of these compounds. Diphenylcarbazine has been

found a suitable indicator. The end-point is marked by the appearance of blue colour.

The simplicity and reliability of the above method prompted us to apply this method to the determination of mercaptans after their transformation to the corresponding organotrithiocarbonates through reaction with carbon disulphide in presence of alkali. The transformation has been found to be extremely fast and quantitative^{3,7}. Though mercury(II) salts have been used for the direct determination of mercaptans, doubts have frequently been expressed over the uniform stoichiometry of the reaction, that is, one or two molecules of mercaptans could react forming both RSHgX and $(\text{RS})_2\text{Hg}$ compounds^{10,11}. These observations in fact lead to the use of organo-mercury compounds (containing only one available mercury valency) in place of mercury(II) salts. The proposed method involving the transformation of mercaptans to organotrithiocarbonates is free from such ambiguity since the stoichiometry of the reaction of mercury(II) with organotrithiocarbonates is clear.

The proposed methods for the determination of organotrithiocarbonates and mercaptans are simple, rapid, accurate and reliable. They possess wide applicability.

Experimental

Mercury(II) acetate, 0.0125 M in water: The solution was standardised as described by Vogel¹².

Organotrithiocarbonates: The compounds were prepared and purified as described earlier^{1,2}. The purity of the compounds was checked by iodimetric titrations³.

Mercaptans: Isopropyl-, isobutyl-, benzyl- and dodecyl mercaptans as well as β -mercaptoethanol and thiophenol were distilled before use. 2-Mercaptobenzothiazol was used as received.

Diphenylcarbazine: 0.1% solution in ethanol.

Procedure:

(a) *Determination of organotrithiocarbonates*: Aliquots of the solution in water of each trithiocarbonate were taken in titration flasks and diluted with 40 ml of water. Each solution was mixed with 0.5 ml of diphenylcarbazine indicator and titrated at room temperature (24°) with standard (0.0125 M) mercury(II) acetate solution. The end-point was marked by the appearance of blue colour. From the volume of standard mercury(II) acetate solution used corresponding to the end-point in each titration, the amount of each trithiocarbonate was calculated. Results are given in Table 1.

(b) *Determination of mercaptans*: To aliquots (1-5 ml) of solutions in acetonitrile of each mercaptan were added another 5 ml of acetonitrile,

TABLE 1—MERCURIMETRIC DETERMINATION OF ORGANOTRITHIOCARBONATES AND MERCAPTANS (THROUGH TRITHIOCARBONATE FORMATION)

Compounds	Values are mean of ten determinations with standard deviation ($\pm$)	
	Amount found*, mg	Amount found**, mg
<i>Organotrithiocarbonates (TTC)</i>		
$\begin{array}{c} \text{RS}-\text{C}-\text{SK} \\ \\ \text{S} \end{array}$		
Benzyl TTC (R, C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂ -)	5.05, 0.063	12.10, 0.080
Dodecyl TTC (R, C ₁₂ H ₂₅ -)	5.04, 0.048	11.90, 0.098
β -Ethanol TTC (R, OHCH ₂ CH ₂ -)	4.96, 0.081	12.09, 0.080
Isopropyl TTC [R, (CH ₃) ₂ CH-]	5.00, 0.052	12.07, 0.101
Isobutyl TTC [R, (CH ₃) ₂ CH-CH ₂ -]	4.95, 0.073	11.88, 0.089
* Amount taken, 5 mg ; **Amount taken, 12 mg		
<i>Mercaptans</i>		
Benzyl mercaptan	4.03, 0.056	10.00, 0.076
Dodecyl mercaptan	4.00, 0.052	10.08, 0.101
β -Mercaptoethanol	3.98, 0.048	9.92, 0.092
Isobutyl mercaptan	4.00, 0.058	10.10, 0.085
Isopropyl mercaptan	3.96, 0.079	9.98, 0.080
Thiophenol	4.03, 0.088	10.03, 0.102
2-Mercaptobenzothiazol	4.05, 0.088	9.91, 0.084
* Amount taken, 4 mg ; **Amount taken, 10 mg		

0.5 ml of carbon disulphide, 5-7 ml of potassium hydroxide (approx. 0.05 N) and 30 ml of water. The contents were shaken and the resulting yellow coloured solution (alkali salts of organotrithiocarbonic acids form yellow coloured solutions) was neutralised with very dilute solution of acetic acid using phenolphthalein as indicator. Diphenylcarbazine indicator (0.5 ml) was added to each solution which was titrated at room temperature (24°) with standard (0.0125 M) mercury(II) acetate solution to the appearance of blue colour. From the volume of titrant used corresponding to the end-point in each titration, the amount of each mercaptan was calculated. Results are given in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

The methods involving mercury(II) reagents have quite extensively been used for the determination of organosulphur compounds. The present communication extends the use of such methods to organotrithiocarbonates. Since these compounds are conveniently prepared from mercaptans, it was considered highly desirable to investigate if the method could be extended so as to determine mercaptans after their conversion to trithiocarbonates. Mercaptan solutions turn yellow immediately on reacting with an excess of carbon disulphide in presence of an alkali, indicating the formation of organotrithiocarbonate (alkali organotrithiocarbonates form yellow solutions). The transformation of mercaptan to trithiocarbonate is immediate. The quantitative nature of this transformation has already been shown by Verma *et al.*^{3,7} and once again by the high accuracy

attained in the determination of mercaptans by this method. The excess of carbon disulphide does not interfere in the analysis of mercaptans. Both organotrithiocarbonates and mercaptans (after conversion to trithiocarbonates) have been successfully titrated with mercury(II) in aqueous medium in pH range 7.5-8.5 using diphenylcarbazine indicator to the appearance of blue colour. The overall standard deviations calculated from the pooled data of all the titrations performed with 5 and 12 mg of each trithiocarbonate have been found to be ± 0.063 and 0.090, respectively (Table 1). The same for 4 and 10 mg of each mercaptan are ± 0.064 and 0.089, respectively (Table 1).

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Determination of Copper in Steel, Brass, Gunmetal, Nickel-Silver and Aluminium Alloy by Extraction with Phenanthraquinone Monothiosemicarbazone

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In this communication we propose a rapid and selective method for the spectrophotometric determination of copper in ferrous and non-ferrous alloys using phenanthraquinone monothiosemicarbazone (PQMT) as the chromogenic reagent